

We hypothesized that there should be no trends in the solved values of Pmax for individual treatments, based on the assumption that our equations account for PAR and LAI effects, and that the QE and Pmax terms account for CO₂ and temperature effects. We then solved for one Pmax value to represent all CO₂ treatments, based on the same assumptions. Pmax thus reflects light-saturated rate at 350 vpm CO₂ and 30°C.

The trend for solved Pmax (of individual chambers) was to increase with increasing CO₂: 17.1, 16.3, 21.9, 29.3, 28.9, and 27.1 μmol CO₂/m² per s at 160, 250, 330, 500, 660, and 900 vpm CO₂, respectively. One solved Pmax (24.0) was adequate to predict canopy response at all CO₂ treatments, except at 160 and 250 vpm. The CO₂-related increase in Pmax and the fact that a single Pmax for all treatments was overpredicted at sub-ambient CO₂ indicated a problem with the assumption that the complete response to CO₂ can be modeled on the basis of energy limitation only.

Electro-transport rate in high light is reported to be inhibited as C_i falls below 300 vpm (Sharkey et al 1988). An asymptotic equation was added to rice Pmax as a function of C_i. This function describes CO₂ substrate limitations upon RuBP regeneration and upon rubisco activity. The 50% response of Pmax to C_i was achieved at 137 vpm CO₂. Figure 1 illustrates how well predicted canopy assimilation matched observed values for 160, 330, and 660 vpm CO₂ treatments using one value for Pmax (29.8 μmol CO₂/m² per s).

In the temperature experiment, rice canopies showed a trend for Pmax to increase from low to high temperature: 18.9, 24.1, 23.0, 24.7, and 39.6 μmol CO₂/m² per s at 25, 28, 31, 34, and 37°C growth/measurement temperature, respectively. Solving for a single Pmax (24.6) to represent all treatments overestimated assimilation at 25 °C and underestimated at higher temperatures.

Temperature effects on efficiency of electron use for CO₂ fixation are accounted for in QE and Pmax, but the equations had no temperature effect on electron transport capacity per se. Adding a linear temperature effect on Pmax

(electron transport) improved the fit considerably.

Linear regression was done for Pmax values vs temperature (10 values from two dates). The equation for temperature effect on Pmax was normalized to 1.0 at 30°C and had a base temperature of 6.4°C (relative = -0.272 + 0.0424°C). Model sensitivity analysis to temperature was then conducted at midday for Pmax = 24.0 μmol CO₂/m² per s, LAI = 5.0, and PAR = 1500 μmol/m² per s. Despite a linear increase in electron transport from 6° to 37°C, predicted canopy gross assimilation was within 98% of maximum from 24° to 32°C at 350 vpm CO₂, and from 28° to 40°C at 700 vpm CO₂ (Fig. 2).

The broad temperature optimum for canopy assimilation is consistent with our

measurements, meaning there were no major differences in canopy assimilation from 25° to 37°C.

REFERENCES CITED

- Baker J T, Allen L H Jr., Boote K J, Jones P. Jones J W (1990) Rice photosynthesis and evapotranspiration in subambient, ambient, and superambient carbon dioxide concentrations. *Agron J.* 82(4):834-840.
- Baker J T, Allen L H Jr, Boote K J (1992) Temperature effects on rice at elevated CO₂ concentration. *J. Exp. Bot.* 43(252): 959-964.
- Boote K J, pickering N B (1994) *Hort. Sci.* (in press)
- Fartquhar G D, von Caemmerer S (1982) Pages 549-587 in *Physiological plant ecology II*. O. L. Lang, ed. Springer-Verlag, Berlin.
- Sharkey T D, Berry J A, Sage R F (1988) *Planta* 176:415-424.

Carbon dioxide and nitrogen fertilizer effects on rice canopy carbon exchange, growth, and yield

J. T. Baker, L. H. Allen, Jr., K. J. Boote, and N. B. Pickering, University of Florida, Gainesville, and United States Department of Agriculture - Agricultural Research Service (USDA-ARS), USA

The current global rise in atmospheric CO₂ is now well-established and is largely attributed to the continuous burning of fossil fuels and large-scale deforestation. The Green Revolution in the tropics was made possible by the development of semidwarf, high-yielding cultivars that were fertilizer-responsive and resistant to lodging (Jennings et al 1979). Nitrogen fertilizer is an important limiting nutrient in the production of modern rice cultivars in Asia (De Datta 1981). The objectives of this study were to determine the effects and possible interactions of CO₂ and N fertilization on the growth, grain yield, and canopy gas exchange (photosynthesis, respiration and evapotranspiration) of rice.

Cultivar IR30 was grown under irrigated conditions in six sunlit controlled-environment plant growth chambers (aboveground dimensions 2 × 1 m cross section × 1.5 m high). Daytime CO₂ concentration was maintained at 330 (three chambers) and at 660 (three chambers) μmol CO₂/mol air. Rice was

direct seeded by hand into 11 rows in each chamber, 0.18 m apart, on 8 Jun 1990. Temperatures were controlled at 28/21/25 °C (daytime dry-bulb air temperature/ nighttime dry-bulb air temperature/flood water temperature). In each CO₂ treatment, N fertilizer (as urea) at 0, 100, or 200 kg/ha was applied to a loamy sand in three splits (1/2, 1/4, and 1/4) at 9, 35, and 59 after planting (DAP). Initial or pre-flood soil pH was 4.8; the NH₄-N 3.5 mg/kg; the NO₃-N, 0.5 mg/kg; and the organic matter content, 4.3%.

Nitrogen fertilization treatments did not significantly affect plant development rates in this experiment while CO₂ treatment effects on development were small. Logistic regression estimates of the day of 50% panicle appearance (near anthesis) indicated no N treatment effects on the number of days to anthesis while CO₂ enrichment tended to decrease the number of days to 50% panicle appearance by about 4-6 d.

Tillering, final biomass accumulation, and grain yield increased with both CO₂ enrichment and increasing N treatment. (See table for final grain yield, yield components, final aboveground biomass, and harvest index.)

As N treatment increased from 0 to 200 kg/ha, grain yields increased from 6.0 to 8.1 and 7.9 to 10.1 Mg/ha for the 330 and 660 mol/mol CO₂ treatments, respectively, because more grain-bearing

panicles were produced with both CO₂ enrichment and increasing N treatment (see table). Similar trends in individual seed mass were observed while filled grains/panicle were apparently unaffected by either CO₂ or N treatment. These trends in grain yield and final aboveground biomass resulted in a decline in harvest index with increasing N treatment (especially in the 660 μmol/mol). Harvest index tended to be higher in the CO₂ enrichment treatments.

Canopy gross photosynthesis and canopy light utilization efficiency were increased by both CO₂ enrichment and increasing N fertilizer throughout the growing season. Canopy dark respiration rate expressed on a ground area basis followed seasonal trends that were similar to those observed for canopy photosynthesis. Canopy dark respiration rates expressed on a plant dry weight basis declined exponentially throughout the growing season and were little affected by either CO₂ or N fertilizer treatments. After complete canopy closure, CO₂ enrichment reduced canopy evapotranspiration and increased canopy photosynthetic water use efficiency.

The effects of CO₂ enrichment at N levels of 100 and 200 kg/ha on growth, grain yield, and canopy gas exchange are similar to our previous CO₂ enrichment studies (Baker et al 1990, 1992a, b). The relatively small plant responses to N fertilizer treatments are attributed to the high native fertility and organic matter content of the soil used in this experiment.

REFERENCES CITED

- Baker J T, Allen L H Jr., Boote K J, Jones P, Jones J W (1990) Rice photosynthesis and evapotranspiration in subambient, ambient and superambient carbon dioxide concentrations. *Agron. J.* 82:834-840
- Baker J T, Laugel F, Boote K J, Allen L H Jr. (1993a) Effects of daytime dioxide concentration on dark respiration on rice. *Plant Cell Environ.* 15:(2)231-239.
- Baker J T, Allen L H Jr., Boote K J (1993b) Temperature effects on rice at elevated CO₂ concentration. *J. Exp. Bot.* 43:959-964.
- De Dana S K. (1981) Principles and practices of rice production. p. 618. John Wiley and Sons. New York.
- Jennings P R, Coffman W R, Kaufman H E (1979) Rice improvement. International Rice Research Institute, P. O. Box 933. Manila, Philippines. ■

Grain yield, components of yield, total above-ground biomass, and harvest index for rice grown in controlled environments chambers.

CO ₂ (μmol/mol)	Nitrogen (kg/ha)	Grain yield (mg/ha)	Panicles (no./plant)	Filled grains (no./panicle)	Individual grain mass (mg/seed)	Aboveground biomass (g/plant)	Harvest Index (g/g)
330	0	6.0	2.8	48.2	18.7	5.5	0.47
	100	8.2	3.3	53.4	20.3	7.3	0.48
	200	8.1	4.0	47.4	18.5	8.1	0.43
660	0	7.9	3.4	49.2	20.6	6.4	0.54
	100	7.9	3.7	49.4	19.6	7.2	0.49
	200	10.1	4.4	53.4	19.2	9.3	0.47
SE ^a		1.46	0.39	7.56	0.97	1.02	0.044
		<i>F value^b</i>					
CO ₂		7.5**	15.4**	0.2 ns	4.1*	4.8*	8.9**
N		8.0**	26.7**	0.5 ns	5.0**	27.1**	6.5**
CO ₂ × N		3.1*	0.5 ns	1.6 ns	6.5**	1.6 ns	16 ns

^aSE in each column is for each of the means and was obtained by pooling each of the within-chamber variances. ^b*, ** = significant at the 0.05 and 0.01 probability levels, respectively. ns = not significant.

Effects of carbon dioxide on competition between rice and barnyard grass

D. M. Olszyk. US Environmental Protection Agency, Corvallis, Oregon, USA, and L. L. Ranasinghe, Oregon State University, Corvallis Oregon, USA

Effects of elevated CO₂ on rice production could occur not only through direct impacts on rice (Baker et al 1990) but also indirectly via ecosystem responses (Bazzaz et al 1985). Preliminary experiments were conducted to test the hypothesis that a C3 crop, rice, and a C4 weed, barnyard grass, respond differently to CO₂, affecting competition between them when grown at different relative densities in the same container.

Rice cultivar IR72 and barnyard grass were grown from seeds obtained from IRRI. Four-day-old seedlings were transplanted into white plastic pots (7.5 cm high × 16.5 cm inner diameter) filled with soil. Plants were arranged in a circle in each pot, with one in the center for the one-plant pots. Plants were watered periodically to maintain standing water with nutrient solution.

Carbon dioxide treatments were provided in individual small-exposure chambers located in a greenhouse with rough temperature and light intensity control but no dewpoint control. Average conditions over two experiments were photosynthetically active radiation (PAR), average daily at 388 μmol/m² per

s; 12 h light period; temperature, average daily maximum of 25.4 °C, average daily minimum of 26.3 °C; and relative humidity, average day period minimum of 42%, average night period maximum, 69%.

Carbon dioxide treatments were ambient (average 374 μL/L), and ambient + continuously added CO₂, resulting in elevated levels of 563, 724, and 895 μL/L. Each CO₂ level occurred in each of two blocks of chambers. Plants were exposed to CO₂ for about 28 d. Seven planting mixtures/densities were examined per chamber (split/plots): 8 barnyard grass, 2 rice and 6 barnyard grass, 4 rice and 4 barnyard grass, 6 rice and 2 barnyard grass, 8 rice, 1 rice, and 1 barnyard grass, with two replicate pots per density per chamber. The experiment was repeated. Both experiments were evaluated together because no significant (at P < 0.05) experiment × CO₂ interactions and few experiment × density interactions were found. Rice and barnyard grass data were analyzed separately (per plant).

Rice plants tended to have increased shoot growth under elevated CO₂ levels. Across densities, elevated CO₂ produced a statistically significant increase in rice leaf number (P < 0.05) (see table), but increases for tiller number and leaf, stem, and total dry weight (Fig. 1) were significant only with P = 0.05-0.16. Few lower P values may be because of, in part, a lack of difference in response among higher CO₂ levels. Density across CO₂ levels had a highly significant effect on all param-